

S4 Table. Representative answers obtained from participants at the end of the 5th Python Workshop for Biological Data, held in 2022.

Question	Category	Answer
How would you improve this course?	Making the notebooks available	"The scripts should be made available because it's difficult to listen to the explanation, type the code, run it, encounter errors, and then go to Discord. It's very easy to get lost and fall behind."
		"Providing the Colabs and study material in advance for study before the lecture."
		"Provision of handouts on the content of the classes, for prior study. I think it would be better for keeping up."
	Workload	"Very extensive workload, sometimes it becomes tiring due to other tasks in our daily lives, and more time for lunch."
		"More days dedicated to Biopython (minimum 2 days)."
		"[...] perhaps distribute the workload better."
Which aspects of this course were most useful or valuable to you?	Content	"Learning to use new tools for data manipulation."
		"The part about creating graphs, like box plots."
		"Understanding the programming logic related to each method/function."
	Methodology	"The entire structure of the course, from the lectures to the workshops, exercise resolutions, and flash talks. It was a very valuable first contact."
		"How to use Python, searching for what you don't know, and the introduction to the main libraries."
		"The applicability of Python in projects developed in the field of biology."
	Networking	"[...] In terms of value, real-time learning, networking, working with peers to develop activities."

The responses contained in the feedback forms were translated from the original language (Portuguese).